

Vibrational spectroscopy characterization of magnetron sputtered silicon oxide and silicon oxynitride films

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ABSTRACT

Vibrational (infrared and Raman) spectroscopy has been used to characterize SiO_xN_y and SiO_x films prepared by magnetron sputtering on steel and silicon substrates. Interference bands in the infrared reflectivity measurements provided the film thickness and the dielectric function of the films. Vibrational modes bands were obtained both from infrared and Raman spectra providing useful information on the bonding structure and the microstructure (formation of nano-voids in some coatings) for these amorphous (or nanocrystalline) coatings. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis have also been carried out to determine the composition and texture of the films, and to correlate these data with the vibrational spectroscopy studies. The angular dependence of the reflectivity spectra provides the dispersion of vibrational and interference polaritons modes, what allows to separate these two types of bands especially in the frequency regions where overlaps/resonances occurred. Finally the attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared measurements have been also carried out demonstrating the feasibility and high sensitivity of the technique. Comparison of the spectra of the SiO_xN_y films prepared in various conditions demonstrates how films can be prepared from pure silicon oxide to silicon oxynitride with reduced oxygen content.

1. Introduction

The silicon microelectronic industry demands drove the attention to silicon based dielectric materials such as silicon oxides, nitrides and oxynitrides as potential materials for integrated optics. This attention has been motivated mainly by their properties such as high resistivity, excellent dielectric strength, large band gap and high melting point.

Amorphous silicon oxide layers have been widely used as insulation between metal and semiconductor layers in integrated circuit technology.

Over the past decades there has been an increasing interest in the preparation and study of silicon oxynitride (SiO_xN_y) thin films. The possibility of tailoring their optical and electrical properties by changing the composition makes them suitable for a large range of applications such as passivation and masking layers in microelec-

tronics, solar cells or luminescent devices [1,2]. Increasing by the other hand the need to understand how the electromagnetic radiation interacts with this material.

In addition the mechanical properties of SiO_xN_y films are known to be strongly dependent on their composition [3]. Silicon oxynitride coatings have been described also as protective coatings for steel [4]. Taking into consideration these applications silicon and steel substrates have been selected to carry out our investigations. Our aim is also to clarify data when comparing results using both types of substrates.

Vibrational spectroscopy (IR and Raman) has a very high chemical and structural sensitivity due to the influence of several material properties (i.e. crystal structure, composition, bonding structure, etc.) on the phonon parameters. These techniques are well suited for nanocrystalline or amorphous materials characterization and are non-destructive. Since the IR and Raman coupling constants are different, these techniques complement each other. In the present work vibrational spectroscopy will be used to characterize SiO_xN_y and SiO_x coatings grown onto steel and silicon.

Although previous works [5–7] have reported the IR analysis for determining the bonding structure of silicon oxide and silicon oxynitride films, these papers are related to coatings prepared by

reactive laser ablation [5], and plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) [6,7]. The IR analysis described in these papers is mainly based on the qualitative assignment of the vibrational modes. In the present paper the infrared spectroscopy is used to characterize films prepared by magnetron sputtering and to determine, not only the bonding structure, but also to get valuable information on thickness and dielectric function. In addition the dispersion analysis of the IR reflectivity spectra at different angles of incidence has been also investigated. The Raman analyses of the

coatings are discussed together with the correlations with compositional data (as obtained by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy—XPS) and microstructural characterization (Scanning electron microscopy—SEM). The formation in some coatings of nano-voids filled with molecular nitrogen has been also demonstrated in

this study.

Attenuated total reflection (ATR) technique was used to study surface polaritons (SP) on the film–vacuum interface. A surface polariton is an evanescent electromagnetic wave that propagates along the interface between two media. The continued scaling down of electronic circuits and devices and the development of new techniques able to produce micron-size materials, has renewed the interest in the study of electromagnetic wave excitation and propagation, particularly on thin films. Surface polaritons are being explored for their potential in subwavelengths optics, magneto-optic data storage, light generation, microscopy, solar cells and bio-photonic sensors [8]. The ATR analysis of the films is also included in this work.

2. Experimental

SiO_xN_y and SiO_x thin films were deposited by r.f. magnetron sputtering from a pure silicon target, under different gas atmospheres. Before deposition the sputtering chamber was evacuated to 1×10^{-4} Pa and pre-heated to 90 °C and the working pressure was kept around of 1.33 Pa. Different sputtering powers and deposition times were used to grow the films. In some cases a dc bias voltage was applied to the substrate. Mirror polished AISI M2 steel and silicon wafers (1 0 0) were the used substrates. Table 1 presents the deposition conditions for the studied samples. Silicon oxynitride coatings were prepared in a N₂ plasma while silicon oxide films were obtained in O₂/Ar plasmas. The nomenclature described in Table 1 includes for each type of samples the sputtering power and the deposition time. In addition the “b” letter indicates a sample growth under substrate bias.

The infrared spectra of SiO_xN_y and SiO_x samples on both substrates (steel and silicon) were measured. Since these substrates are not transparent for IR radiation, the reflection mode of the technique was used. Reflectivity measurements in the spectral range 50–7500 cm⁻¹, were carried out using an IFS66v (BRUKER) infrared Fourier-transform spectrometer with reflection unit at near normal incidence. The spectral resolution was 2 cm⁻¹. IR reflectivity spectra showed vibrational bands and strong interference bands which allowed the calculation of the film

Table 1
Deposition conditions of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x films.

Sample	N ₂ (Pa)	O ₂ (Pa)	Ar (Pa)	Power rf (W)	Bias dc (V)	<i>t</i> (h) ^a	<i>d</i> (nm) SEM
SiON-150/3	1.33	–	–	150	–	3	481
SiON-250/3	1.33	–	–	250	–	3	
SiON-300/3	1.33	–	–	300	–	3	800
SiON-300b/3	1.33	–	–	300	500	3	513
SiO-150/6	–	0.53	0.80	150	–	6	1970
SiO-250/1	–	0.53	0.80	250	–	1	2280
SiO-250/2	–	0.53	0.80	250	–	2	

^a Deposition time.

thickness and dielectric function. The experimental spectra were compared with the simulations calculated using Fresnel equation for a film of a thickness *d*. The frequency dependence of the film dielectric function was represented as a sum of high frequency dielectric constant ϵ_{∞} , a set of Lorentz oscillators and free carrier plasma (Drude) contribution:

$$\epsilon(\eta) = \epsilon_{\infty} + \frac{\mathbf{P} f_i^2}{\eta_i^2 - \eta^2 - i g_i \eta} + \frac{f_p^2}{-\eta^2 - i \eta \Gamma} \quad (1)$$

For silicon or metal substrate:

$$\epsilon(\eta) = \epsilon_{\infty} + \frac{f_p^2}{-\eta^2 - i \eta \Gamma} \quad (2)$$

where η_i is the *i*th vibrational mode frequency, f_i is its oscillator strength, g_i is its width, f_p is the plasma frequency, Γ is the carrier collision frequency in plasma. Spectra fitting, varying both film and substrate parameters were done using SCOUT—Spectroscopic Objects and Utilities, a WINDOWS application written by Theiß [9,10].

The reflectivity spectra of silicon oxynitride films were measured at 158, 208, 308, 408, 508, 608, 708 and 808 angles of incidence. The film polariton dispersion was calculated using 3-media dispersion equation (Eq. (3)) [11,12] with dielectric functions parameters obtained above.

$$(b_1 + b_2)(b_2 + b_3) + (b_1 - b_2)(b_2 - b_3) \exp(-2dk_2) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $b_i = k_i$ for transverse electric (TE) modes and $b_i = e_i/k_i$ for

transverse magnetic (TM) modes, $k_i = \sqrt{c^2 - \epsilon_i} / c$, $k_x = \sin(\theta)$

for the angle of incidence θ .

The attenuated total reflection measurements have been done using IFS66v (BRUKER) infrared Fourier-transform spectrometer. In this technique, the sample is placed close (with the vacuum gap of the order of the wavelength) to a reflecting prism of a high refractive index. At angles of incidence bigger than the angle of total internal reflection for prism–gap interface surface polaritons can be excited causing the total reflection decrease. Total reflection occurs at the sample/prism interface, and all reflection losses are due to absorption processes within the sample.

The ATR unit with KRS-5 prism (NPVO-1, LOMO) was used for various angles of incidence (20–60) in p-polarized light. The grid polarizer on KRS-5 substrate was used. The spectral resolution was 2 cm⁻¹.

A spectrograph TRIAX with special corrective optics, on an axis triple grating turret, with a Notch filter and CCD camera was used for the investigation of the Raman scattering light ($F = 550$ mm; 100, 600 and 1800 grooves/mm). The line at 514.5 nm of an Ar-laser was used for the excitation of the Raman scattering. The spectral resolution was about 5 cm⁻¹. The spectrograph system supports two experimental configurations: (i) macro-Raman spectroscopy and (ii) micro-Raman spectroscopy. In this work, the setup of micro-Raman spectroscopy with a microscope which provided a focus diameter of one micrometer was chosen. Since the Raman signal of steel substrates is weaker than the silicon substrates the Raman spectra were measured of samples grown onto steel.

The XPS equipment was a Leybold Heraeus LH10 spectrometer working in the constant analyzer energy mode with a pass-energy of 50 eV. The binding energy reference was taken as the main component of the C1s peak at 284.6 eV for adventitious carbon. For quantification the XPS spectra were subjected to background subtraction (Shirley background) and sensitivity factors supplied by the instrument manufacturer were used.

Scanning electron microscopy was performed to study the morphology of samples in a HITACHI S-4800 SEM-FEG microscope. The samples were cleaved from coatings grown onto silicon, an

Table 2
XPS surface analysis of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x films.

Sample	Si (at.%)	N (at.%)	O (at.%)	C (at.%)	Auger parameter ^a	
					\mathfrak{a}_1	\mathfrak{a}_2
SiON-150/3	36.9	32.4	25.9	4.8	1713.9	1713.3
SiON-250/3	38.2	30.9	24	6.9	1713.9	1714
SiON-300/3	38.1	27.3	28.8	5.8	1714.3	1714
SiON-300b/3	38.2	40.6	16.9	4.3	1714.2	1714.1
SiO-150/6	25.9	—	71.7	2.4	1711.7	1711.6
SiO-250/1	27.2	—	67.7	5.1	1711.8	1711.7
SiO-250/2	35.2	—	61.7	3.1	1711.8	1712.2

^a Auger parameter of Si: binding energy of Si2p photoelectron peak plus kinetic energy of Si KLL Auger peak. Data for samples before (\mathfrak{a}_1) and after (\mathfrak{a}_2) Ar + bombardment for surface cleaning.

were observed without metallization in cross sectional views at 1 kV.

3. Results and their discussion

3.1. Microstructural and compositional analysis

Table 2 summarizes the compositional analysis of the coatings as measured by XPS after argon bombardment to clean the surface, also the Auger parameter of silicon (binding energy of Si2p photoelectron peak plus kinetic energy of Si KLL Auger peak) is presented for samples before (\mathfrak{a}_1) and after (\mathfrak{a}_2) Ar + bombardment. The two series of coatings appear, from the point of view of composition, as silicon oxynitride and silicon oxide when prepared in a N_2 plasma or in an O_2/Ar plasma respectively.

The incorporation of oxygen to the SiO_xN_y coatings cannot be avoided in our experimental conditions even by working in pure N_2 plasma due to the presence of activated oxygen species as a consequence of the partial oxygen pressure in the residual vacuum of the chamber. The high reactivity of oxygen towards silicon leads to immediate oxidation of the deposition target. In addition the absence of a shutter which allows cleaning the sputtering target before deposition, can also contribute to the introduction of oxygen in the films due to surface oxidation of the Si target by air exposure.

The unavoidable incorporation of oxygen in these kinds of coatings has been reported by other authors [13–15]. Particularly Oliveira [15] presents results indicating the increasing of oxygen incorporation in the films with the increase of deposition pressure. In his case, for a deposition pressure of 1 Pa (with a power density of 6.25 W cm^{-2}), 30 at.% of oxygen was incorporated in the film. He claims that this oxygen incorporation is probably due to the low deposition rate, which allows the formation of silicon oxides by the residual oxygen present in the deposition chamber. These values are similar to ours (1.33 Pa with a power density of 7.4 W cm^{-2} , 25.9 at.% of oxygen in the film).

We have also evaluated the Auger parameter of Si before (\mathfrak{a}_1) and after bombardment (\mathfrak{a}_2) to clean the surface from adventitious contaminations. The obtained values for SiO_xN_y samples (in Table 2) are very similar for all coatings and characteristic of silicon oxynitride, proving the nature of these films [16]. The reproducibility of oxygen incorporation in these films has been therefore proved in our system and also in the works from Oliveira, Yao and Vila [15,13,14].

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x samples grown onto silicon.

Nevertheless it was found that working under high sputtering power and substrate bias conditions is reducing very efficiently the oxygen content of the silicon oxynitride films. The effect of substrate bias on the oxygen concentration in silicon nitride coatings was also observed by Oliveira et al. [15] and Kim and

Chung [17]. A clear decrease is observed when bias is applied. When substrate bias is applied the energetic substrate bombardment causes a decrease in oxygen content of the film through preferential resputtering. By the other hand bias appliance during deposition causes changes on the microstructure of the films which can decrease the oxidation by air exposure after deposition [17].

In the case of silicon oxide coatings the increase in deposition power results in an increase of silicon content in the films due to the higher deposition rate. For the sample SiO-150/1 the oxidation rate of the sputtering target is higher than the deposition rate and sputtering occurs on the oxidized target surface. Similar results were observed by Ohwaki and Taga [18].

The microstructural information is presented in Fig. 1 for representative coatings. For the SiON-150/3 and SiON-300b/3 samples grown onto silicon it is clearly observed (Fig. 1a) that increasing the sputtering power and introducing a substrate bias increases the densification and compaction of the film. It is worth of mention that at low sputtering power an incipient columnar structure is observed together with an intrinsic closed porosity formed by small spherical pores (nano-voids) distributed all along the coating.

For the SiO-150/6 and SiO-250/1 samples, also deposited onto silicon, it is again clearly observed (Fig. 1b) that increasing the sputtering power is producing the compaction of the film. A clear columnar structure is hereby observed for low sputtering power. The columnar structure is typical of coatings grown under low energetic ion bombardment and limited adatom mobility [19]. It is also possible to see the voids between the columns, characteristic of zone 1 in Thornton's model [19].

3.2. Infrared reflectivity measurements at near normal incidence

The infrared spectra for the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x series of samples deposited onto steel substrates are displayed in Fig. 2 for representative samples.

Fig. 2a shows the IR reflectivity spectra for the SiON-150/3 and SiON-300b/3 samples grown onto steel and for the SiON-300b/3 sample grown onto silicon for comparison purposes. Reflectivity spectra are widely used to study thin films on opaque substrates. As a rule the reflection spectra of such samples show two types of bands: (i) absorption at frequencies of dipole vibrations in the film material; (ii) a set of interference bands because the film looks like the Fabry–Perot interferometer. From analytical point of view it is very important to separate these two types of bands and especially in frequency regions where there are resonances of vibrational and interference modes [20]. As it can be observed in Fig. 2a the spectra on steel substrates show less intense interference bands what allow a better identification of the vibrational modes. This effect has been observed in all the investigated samples and the spectra for coatings grown on steel substrates have been selected for the analysis of reflectivity spectra at near normal incidence.

Samples SiON-150/3 and SiON-300b/3 were prepared with the same deposition time at different sputtering power and bias (Table 1). The most intense band appears in the 700–900 cm^{-1} range and can be attributed to SiON species [5–7] once more confirming the formation of silicon oxynitride. In fact the position of this band can vary by intrinsic structural changes [21] caused by stress and also by changing the composition of the oxynitride phases [5–7]. Silicon oxide bands above 1000 cm^{-1} can be also detected in samples SiON-150/3 and SiON-300b/3 (Fig. 2a)

Fig. 2. Infrared spectra of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x samples grown onto steel. The spectrum for the sample SiON-300b/3 grown onto silicon is also included.

but they are much weaker than the silicon oxynitride ones. Characteristics bands can be identified and attributed to SiO (ca. 1000 cm^{-1}) and SiO_2 (450, 800 and 1050–1200 cm^{-1}). The presence of Si–O bonds is clearly observed in the sample SiON-150/3 while for the SiON-300b/3 sample a shoulder is detected at the high wavenumber site of the strong SiON band. According to the compositional data recorded by XPS and summarized in Table 2, the sample grown at higher voltage with substrate bias is the one containing less oxygen. This result demonstrates that at higher power and substrate bias the incorporation of oxygen from the residual vacuum during growth of the film is less important. For the SiON-300/3 and the SiON-250/3 samples the XPS analysis also shows the formation of oxynitride phases. In these cases the oxygen content is always smaller than on samples prepared with a power 150 W at the silicon target. These samples, that present a strong overlapping of vibrational and interference bands, will be also studied by taking into consideration the angular dependence of the infrared reflectivity spectra and by using the attenuated total reflection mode as shown bellow.

SiH and OH (NH) bands can also be distinguished in the SiON-150/3 sample (Fig. 2a). SiH groups appear typically in the 2100–2300 cm^{-1} range while the bands at 1700 and 3500 cm^{-1} are characteristic of OH (or NH groups) and are probably due to the adsorption of water molecules onto the surface (or open pores) of the SiON_x (or SiO_x see bellow) coatings. Similar bands have been also observed in a previous work (for SiCN films) [22]. The microstructure of the films (Fig. 1a) is showing an incipient

columnar structure for the SiON-150/3 sample as compared to SiON-300b/3. The presence of porosity in addition to the higher content in oxygen (silica formation), will favor the water adsorption and the apparition of OH (or NH) bands for the sample prepared at low sputtering power. The more dense structures without open porosity, obtained at higher power and bias, are the most adequate from the point of view of applications.

The SiO_x samples (SiO-250/1 and SiO-150/6) were deposited using the same gas mixture (O₂/(O₂ + Ar) = 40%) and different deposition times and sputtering power intensity (Table 1). In this case, the infrared spectra of the samples (Fig. 2b) indicate that the most intense bands can be attributed to SiO and SiO₂ groups. In fact the bands attributed to SiO (ca. 1000 cm⁻¹) and all the SiO₂ characteristics bands (450, 800 and 1050–1200 cm⁻¹) can be clearly observed.

SiH and OH bands can also be clearly distinguished in this series of samples (Fig. 2b). In addition to the already mentioned OH bands at 1700 and 3500 cm⁻¹, typical bands for SiH groups at 2100–2300 cm⁻¹ are detected. The presence of these bands is related to the water absorption capacity of silica coatings.

The IR spectra for the same samples deposited onto silicon substrate are consistent with those for the samples deposited onto steel although there is a strong overlapping of vibrational and interference bands. It was concluded then, that the bonding structure of the growing films is not influenced by the type of substrate.

The high frequency dielectric constant (ϵ_{∞}) and thickness of the samples were calculated from the IR spectra, the results are given in Table 3. The estimated values of thickness are consistent with data obtained by SEM analysis (see Table 1).

The ϵ_{∞} value and the oxide bands frequencies in Fig. 2b for the SiO_x samples are typical for SiO₂ films. For the sample grown at higher sputtering power the ϵ_{∞} value is higher, it corresponds to a more dense and compact sample as stated by SEM analysis.

The introduction of N in the films produces in the SiON-150/3, SiON-250/3, SiON-300/3 and SiON-300b/3 an increase in dielectric constant as expected for silicon nitride coatings. Silicon oxynitride coatings are known to have tailored optical properties varying from those of silicon oxide to silicon nitride by changing its stoichiometry [23,24]. The sample grown at 300 W with substrate bias shows the highest dielectric constant value, related to the lower oxygen content and the higher density of this film. In general a correlation was found between dielectric constant of the films, composition and microstructure. It is important to mention here that for the SiON-150/3 coating we expect an extra diminution of the dielectric constant value due to the presence of close porosity (nano-voids) as detected by SEM (Fig. 1) [25]. This microstructure explains therefore the low value of ϵ_{∞} found for this coating.

3.3. Raman results

The results of Raman spectra for the studied samples are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 3a presents the results for the selected SiO_xN_y,

Table 3
High frequency dielectric constant and thickness of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x films as calculated from IR reflectivity spectra.

Sample	ϵ_{∞}	d (nm) IR
SiON-150/3	2.77	540
SiON-250/3	2.82	950
SiON-300/3	3.50	860
SiON-300b/3	3.52	510
SiO-150/6	2.04	2300
SiO-250/1	2.44	2250
SiO-250/2	2.35	4100

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of the SiO_xN_y and SiO_x samples deposited onto steel.

samples. Several features can be investigated and assigned according to previous works: characteristic Si–N (or Si–O–N) Raman peaks appear in the 800–1100 cm⁻¹ [26] range; a narrow band at 1006 cm⁻¹ is most probably assigned to SiN_x (or SiO_xN_y) nanocrystallites [27]; the peak at 480 cm⁻¹ can be due to Si–O species (as described below for the SiO_x samples) and the narrow band at 2330 cm⁻¹ is clearly assigned to molecular nitrogen (N₂). For sample SiON-150/3 deposited in pure nitrogen, we can observe in addition to typical features in the Si–N region (840–1020 cm⁻¹), an intense band in the position of molecular nitrogen that can be attributed to the encapsulation of nitrogen into the closed pores during the growth of the films. The closed porosity observed by SEM (Fig. 1a) is filled with molecular nitrogen trapped during

deposition. For the sample SiON-300b/3, deposited in similar conditions but with a higher sputtering power (300 W) and substrate bias, the Raman spectrum shows a narrow band at 1006 cm^{-1} attributed to the SiN (or SiO_xN_y) nanocrystallites and also a band at 480 cm^{-1} in the region of Si–O modes. In general it has been found that at higher sputtering powers the bands appear narrower and better formed than for the sample prepared at lower sputtering power what indicates that only under high power conditions it was possible to obtain a certain degree of order in these coatings mostly amorphous. No molecular nitrogen could be detected in the SiON-300b/3 sample as corresponds to the absence of closed pores inside this sample. The Raman spectra of both samples are therefore consistent with the presence of Si–O and Si–N (or Si–O–N) bonds and the bonding structure could be identified even for these amorphous (or nanocrystalline) structures. These results are in agreement with XPS results summarized in Table 2.

The Raman spectra of the SiO_x samples are presented in Fig. 3b. For the SiO-150/6 sample the specific Raman features can be attributed to vitreous silica $v\text{-SiO}_2$, in agreement with previously reported bands at 498, 605, 810 and 1030 cm^{-1} [28]. An additional band at 975 cm^{-1} appears usually in silicate glasses and it is attributed to $(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6)_n$ chains [29]. The weak bands in the $1400\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region belong to the carbon modes for carbon contamination of the films. For the SiO-250/1 sample the spectrum show more intense and well defined bands as compared to the sample grown at lower sputtering power. Raman appears to be more sensitive than IR for microstructural changes associated to the formation of very small nanocrystals [30]. The observed spectra correspond to a higher degree of structural order for the sample prepared at higher power as compared with the more amorphous SiO-150/6 sample. The degree of order in the coatings is mainly influenced by the sputtering power. The observed spectrum for the

SiO-250/1 sample is consistent with the formation of SiO and SiO_2 phases.

3.4. Angular dependence of infrared reflectivity spectra

Valuable information about solids can be obtained from the study of polaritons as coupled states of modes of medium (phonons, excitons, etc.) with the electromagnetic field. Reflectivity spectra, widely used to study thin films on opaque substrates, can be applied to study polaritons in the optical region [8,10]. In particular the separation of vibrational and interference bands will be possible if we can reconstruct the dispersion of the polaritons (wave vector dependence of the frequency: $V(k_x)$) of the sample from experimental spectra. The dispersion of interference polaritons (Fabry–Perot or cavity modes) is different from dispersion of vibrational (phonon) polaritons. To show how this procedure applied to the coatings under investigation, we have selected the reflectivity spectra obtained for the SiON-300/3 sample grown onto silicon substrates. This sample is the thicker one from all SiO_xN_y coatings and therefore the one showing a higher number on interference polaritons which can overlap with vibrational bands. In this case the here presented procedure will be very valuable.

Fig. 4 shows infrared reflectivity spectra of the SiON-300/3 sample for s-polarized light (TE modes) and p-polarized light (TM modes) at different incidence angles (curves a and c). Several vibrational bands and 2 strong interference bands can be found in these spectra. The positions of minima were considered as the polaritons frequencies. The film thicknesses and the dielectric functions were obtained from these spectra using the SCOUT fitting procedure as previously described. The calculated values for this sample are also included in Table 3. The SiN and Si–O–N bands in the $700\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region were detected together with the less

Fig. 4. IR reflectivity spectra of the SiON-300/3 sample in s-polarized light (TE modes) (a) and p-polarized light (TM modes) (c) at some angles of incidence (shown in degrees on figure legends). Polaritons dispersion curves for TE modes (b) and TM modes (d).

intense bands attributed to SiO ($\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and SiO₂ (450, 800 and 1050–1200 cm^{-1}) species.

Calculated and experimental dispersion curves of the polaritons for the SiON-300/3 coating are shown in Fig. 4 (curves b and d). Note the steps in the TM interference polaritons dispersion curves due to phase jumps at the Brewster angle of incidence [31]. There are therefore two interference polaritons, and between them a vibrational polariton ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, OH and NH groups) appears. It is interesting to note the intersection of the lower interference TM polariton branch and the vibrational polariton branch. This example clearly illustrates how the merely qualitative analysis of peaks from near normal incidence reflectivity curves can lead in some cases to miss assignment.

3.5. Attenuated total reflection (ATR) measurements

Attenuated total reflection is a powerful method for the investigation of thin films by IR spectroscopy. Fig. 5 shows the ATR spectra measured at different angles of incidence both on silicon and steel substrates for samples SiON-250/3 (a and b), SiON-150/3 (c and d) and SiO-250/2 (e and f). Angular dependencies of the absorption bands (related to Si–O and Si–O–N bonds) in ATR spectra give the dispersion of surface polaritons on the film–vacuum interface. The surface polaritons occur in the spectral regions where the material’s dielectric function is negative, therefore they can be used for reconstruction of dielectric function of the film $\epsilon(V)$ in the regime $\epsilon' < 0$.

Fig. 5. ATR spectra of SiON-250/3 (a and b), SiON-150/3 (c and d) and SiO-250/2 (e and f) samples grown onto silicon (a, c, and e) and steel (b, d and f). The angles of incidence are shown near the curves. The arrows show vibrational polaritons frequencies.

Looking to the spectra we can find the bands characteristics for various groups. So, infrared bands at 450, 800 and 1050–1200 cm^{-1} can be attributed to silicon dioxide, the bands near 1000 cm^{-1} to silicon monoxide and the bands in the range 700–900 cm^{-1} to silicon nitride/silicon oxynitride depending on the composition. These bands are indicated by the arrows in Fig. 5. We do not consider here more high frequency but weaker bands (related to SiH, CH, OH or NH vibrations). The sensitivity of the ATR technique is well demonstrated in these spectra especially in the samples deposited on steel. The analysis of the observed bands shows how the control of the composition in the gas phase allows the controlled preparation of pure oxide as well as oxynitride films. The sample prepared in nitrogen plasma at higher sputtering power is the one with less oxygen content among the samples presented in Fig. 5. Consequently is the one presenting also a stronger band in the Si–O–N region and weaker Si–O characteristic bands.

4. Conclusions

Two series of samples were prepared as silicon oxynitride and silicon oxide coatings by magnetron sputtering of a silicon target in a N_2 plasma or in an O_2/Ar plasma respectively. The use of high sputtering powers and substrate bias conditions is reducing the oxygen content in the SiO_xN_y coatings. In addition the use of high sputtering powers is enhancing the compaction of the films. Columnar or porous structures could only be detected at low sputtering powers.

The characteristic bands for several chemical groups appear in the IR spectra (Fig. 2). Particularly, the infrared bands at 450, 800 and 1050–1200 cm^{-1} can be attributed to silicon dioxide, the band near 1000 cm^{-1} corresponds to silicon monoxide, 700–900 cm^{-1} is due to silicon oxynitride (varying with the composition), 2100–2300 cm^{-1} belongs to SiH groups, and the bands near 1700 and 3500 cm^{-1} are attributed to OH (or NH) vibrations.

For the Raman spectra (Fig. 3) typical bands appear for vitreous silica ($\nu\text{-SiO}_2$) at 498, 605, 810 and 1030 cm^{-1} . The band at 975 cm^{-1} appears usually in silicate glasses and it is attributed to $(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6)_n$ chains. Characteristic Si–N (or Si–O–N) Raman peaks appear in the 800–1100 cm^{-1} range; a narrow band at 1007 cm^{-1} is most probably assigned to SiN_x (or SiO_xN_y) nanocrystallites; the peak at 480 cm^{-1} can be due to Si–O species and the narrow band at 2330 cm^{-1} is clearly assigned to molecular nitrogen (N_2) trapped into some of the films.

The qualitative analysis by IR and Raman of vibrational modes in reflectivity spectra (recorded at near normal incidence), provided useful information on the bonding structure of amorphous or nanocrystalline coatings which are difficult to investigate by other techniques. The SiON_x coatings consist of an amorphous or nanocrystalline network of Si–O–N with a lower amount of Si–O and Si–H bonds. The presence of OH and NH groups has been attributed to the adsorption of water onto the films surface. The presence of molecular nitrogen has been attributed to its encapsulation in closed pores inside the SiO_xN_y films during growth at low sputtering powers. The SiO_x series showed either SiO_2 or a mixture of SiO_2 and SiO oxides depending on the deposition parameters. Other species such as $\nu\text{-SiO}_2$ and $(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_6)_n$ were observed in these samples. As a summary we can conclude that the IR, Raman and XPS analysis provided a clear evidence of the formation of silicon oxynitride and silicon oxide coatings depending on the experimental conditions.

The quantitative analysis of the interference bands in the reflectivity spectra allows obtaining film thickness and dielectric function which were correlated with compositional and microstructural analysis of the films. Changing the composition in SiO_xN_y allows to tailor the optical and electrical properties. In addition for

similar compositions, microstructural changes can be introduced to modify the dielectric function by the presence of close porosity in the films. The measurement of the thin film reflectivity at different angles allows drawing the radiative polariton dispersion curves and separate vibrational and interference polaritons, this is providing complementary conclusions about the species present in the films. These curves are also in a reasonable agreement with those calculated using the film parameters obtained from the dispersion analysis of the spectra.

The attenuated total reflection technique coupled to the FT infrared has been demonstrated as a valuable technique for the characterization of these types of coatings.

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